

Reference List for: Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2020). Verfälschungsverhalten in Psychologischer Diagnostik. Report Psychologie, 45(9), 16–23.

Author: Jessica Röhner

Date: June 13, 2025

This document contains the full reference list from the article: “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2020). Verfälschungsverhalten in Psychologischer Diagnostik. Report Psychologie, 45(9), 16–23.” The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

References

- Alfano, K. & Boone, K. B. (2007).** The use of effort tests in the context of actual versus feigned attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder and learning disability. In K. B. Boone (Hrsg.), *Assessment of feigned cognitive impairment: A neuropsychological perspective* (pp. 366–383). New York: Guilford.
- Beauducel, A. & Kersting, M. (2010).** *START-P, Testbatterie für Berufseinsteiger* (1. Aufl.). Göttingen: Hogrefe.
- Bensch, D., Maaß, U., Greiff, S., Horstmann, K. T. & Ziegler, M. (2019).** The nature of faking: A homogeneous and predictable construct? *Psychological Assessment, 31* (4), 532–544.
- Birkeland, S. A., Manson, T. M., Kisamore, J. L., Brannick, M. T. & Smith, M. A. (2006).** A meta-analytic investigation of job applicant faking on personality measures. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment, 14* (4), 317–335.
- Brickenkamp, R. (2002).** *d2-R, Aufmerksamkeits-Belastungs-Test* (9., überarbeitete und neu normierte Aufl.). Göttingen: Hogrefe.
- Burns, G. N. & Christiansen, N. D. (2006).** Sensitive or senseless: On the use of social desirability measures in selection and assessment. In R. L. Griffith & M. H. Peterson (Hrsg.), *A closer examination of applicant faking behavior* (pp. 115–150). Greenwich: Information Age.
- Burns, G. N., Fillipowski, J. N., Morris, M. B. & Shoda, E. A. (2015).** Impact of electronic warnings on online personality scores and test-taker reactions in an applicant simulation. *Computers in Human Behavior, 48*, 163–172.
- Burns, G. N. & Shoda, E. A. (2017).** Putting applicant faking effects on personality tests into context. *Journal of Managerial Psychology, 32* (6), 460–468.

Clemow, D. B. & Walker, D. J. (2014). The potential for misuse and abuse of medications in ADHD: A review. *Postgraduate Medicine*, 126 (5), 64–81.

DePaulo, B. M., Kirkendol, S. E., Kashy, D. A., Wyer, M. M. & Epstein, J. A. (1996). Lying in everyday life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 70 (5), 979–995.

Diagnostik- und Testkuratorium (2018). TBS-DTK. Testbeurteilungssystem des Diagnostik- und Testkuratoriums der Föderation Deutscher Psychologinnenvereinigungen. Revidierte Fassung vom 3. Januar 2018. *Psychologische Rundschau*, 69, 109–116.

Dilchert, S. & Ones, D. S. (2012). Application of preventive strategies. In M. Ziegler, C. MacCann, & R. D. Roberts (Hrsg.), *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment* (pp. 177–200). New York: Oxford University Press.

Donovan, J. J., Dwight, S. A. & Hurtz, G. M. (2003). An assessment of the prevalence, severity, and verifiability of entry-level applicant faking using the randomized response technique. *Human Performance*, 16 (1), 81–106.

Donovan, J. J., Dwight, S. A. & Schneider, D. (2014). The impact of applicant faking on selection measures, hiring decisions, and employee performance. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29 (3), 479–493.

Dunnette, M. D., McCartney, J., Carlson, H. C. & Kirchner, W. K. (1962). A study of faking behavior on a forced-choice self-description checklist. *Personnel Psychology*, 15 (1), 13–24.

Fahrenberg, J., Hampel, R. & Selg, H. (2010). *FPI-R, Freiburger Persönlichkeitsinventar* (8., erweiterte Aufl.). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Flehmig, H. C., Steinborn, M., Langner, R. Scholz, A. & Westhoff, K. (2007). Assessing intraindividual variability in sustained attention tasks: reliability, relation to speed and accuracy, and practice effects. *Psychology Science*, 49 (2), 132–149.

Goffin, R. D. & Boyd, A. C. (2009). Faking and personality assessment in personnel selection: Advancing models of faking. *Canadian Psychology*, 50 (3), 151–160.

Goffin, R. D. & Christiansen, N. D. (2003). Correcting personality tests for faking: A review of popular personality tests and an initial survey of researchers. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 11 (4), 340–344.

Greve, K. W., Ord, J. S., Bianchini, K. J. & Curtis, K. L. (2009). Prevalence of malingering in patients with chronic pain referred for psychologic evaluation in a medico-legal context. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 90 (7), 1117–1126.

Griffith, R. L., Chmielowski, T. & Yoshita, Y. (2007). Do applicants fake? An examination of the frequency of applicant faking behavior. *Personnel Review*, 36 (3), 341–355.

Griffith, R. L., Peterson, M. H., Quist, J. S., Benda, A. & Evans, A. (2008). Faking the personality profile: Easier said than done. In R. L. Griffith & M. H. Peterson (Chairs), *Complex problems, simple solutions: Contemporary research in applied faking behavior*. Symposium

presented at the 23rd Annual Conference for the Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology, San Francisco, CA, USA.

Kersting, M. (2004). Zur Bedeutung der Validität und der sozialen Akzeptanz in der Berufseignungsdiagnostik. *Zeitschrift für Personalpsychologie*, 3 (2), 83–86.

Kubinger, K. D. (2009). *Psychologische Diagnostik: Theorie und Praxis psychologischen Diagnostizierens* (2., überarbeitete und erweiterte Aufl.). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Law, S. J., Bourdage, J. & O'Neill, T. A. (2016). To fake or not to fake: Antecedents to interview faking, warning instructions, and its impact on applicant reactions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 1771.

Levashina, J. & Campion, M. A. (2007). Measuring faking in the employment interview: Development and validation of an interview faking behavior scale. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92 (6), 1638–1656.

MacCann, C., Ziegler, M. & Roberts, R. D. (2012). Faking in personality assessment: Reflections and Recommendations. In M. Ziegler, C. MacCann, & R. D. Roberts (Hrsg.), *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment* (pp. 309–329). Oxford: University Press.

Marcus, B. (2009). 'Faking' from the applicant's perspective: A theory of self-presentation in personnel selection settings. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 17 (4), 417–430.

Mittenberg, W., Patton, C., Canyock, E. M. & Condit, D. C. (2002). Base rates of malingering and symptom exaggeration. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology*, 24, 1094-1102.

Moosbrugger, H. & Kelava, A. (2012). Qualitätsanforderungen an einen psychologischen Test (Testgütekriterien). In H. Moosbrugger, & A. Kelava (Hrsg.), *Testtheorie und Fragebogenkonstruktion* (S. 8–26). Berlin: Springer.

Novak, S. P., Kroutil, L. A., Williams, R. L. & Van Brunt, D. L. (2007). The nonmedical use of prescription ADHD medications: Results from a national Internet panel. *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention, and Policy*, 2, 32.

Pella, R. D., Hill, B. D., Shelton, J. T., Elliott, E. & Gouvier, W. D. (2012). Evaluation of embedded malingering indices in a non-litigating clinical sample using control, clinical, and derived groups. *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 27 (1), 45–57.

Robinson, E. V. & Rogers, R. (2015). Empathy faking in psychopathic offenders: The vulnerability of empathy measures. *Journal of Psychopathological Behavior Assessment*, 37, 545–552.

Rodd, J. (2019). How to maintain data quality when you can't see your participants. *The Observer*, 32, 32–35.

Röhner, J. & Ewers, T. (2016). Trying to separate the wheat from the chaff: Construct- and faking-related variance on the Implicit Association Test (IAT). *Behavior Research Methods*, 48 (1), 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-015-0568-1>

Röhner, J., Schröder-Abé, M. & Schütz, A. (2011). Exaggeration is harder than understatement, but practice makes perfect! Faking success in the IAT. *Experimental Psychology*, 58 (6), 464–472. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1618-3169/a000114>

Röhner, J., Schröder-Abé, M. & Schütz, A. (2013). What do fakers actually do to fake the IAT? An investigation of faking strategies under different faking conditions. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 47 (4), 330–338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2013.02.009>

Röhner, J. & Schütz, A. (2016). *Psychologie der Kommunikation* (2., überarbeitete und erweiterte Auflage). Wiesbaden: Springer VS. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-10024-7>

Röhner, J. & Schütz, A. (2019a). Faking behavior. In V. Zeigler-Hill and T. K. Schmidt-Shackelford (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences* (pp. 1553–1558). New York: Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_2341-1

Röhner, J. & Schütz, A. (2019b). Fälschung(-sverhalten). In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (S. 584). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Röhner, J. & Schütz, A. (2019c). Unverfälschbarkeit. In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (S. 1847). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Röhner, J. & Thoss, P. J. (2018). EZ: An easy way to conduct a more fine-grained analysis of faked and nonfaked Implicit Association Test (IAT) data. *The Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 14 (1), 17–35. <https://doi.org/10.20982/tqmp.14.1.p017>

Rosse, J. G., Stecher, M. D., Miller, J. L. & Levin, R. A. (1998). The impact of response distortion on preemployment personality testing and hiring decisions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83 (4), 634–644.

Rynes, S. L. (1993). Who's selecting whom? Effects of selection practices on applicant attitudes and behavior. In N. Schmitt & W. C. Borman (Eds.), *Personnel Selection in Organizations* (pp. 240–274). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Salgado, J. F. (2016). A theoretical model of psychometric effects of faking on assessment procedures: Empirical findings and implications for personality at work. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 24 (3), 209–228.

Sansone, R. A. & Sansone, L. A. (2011). Faking attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. *Innovations in Clinical Neuroscience*, 8 (8), 10–13.

Schmidt-Atzert, L., Bühner, M., Rischen, S. & Warkentin, V. (2004). Erkennen von Simulation und Dissimulation im Test d2. *Diagnostica*, 50, 124–133.

Smith, D. B. & McDaniel, M. (2011). Questioning old assumptions: Faking and the personality-performance relationship. In M. Zeigler, C. MacCann, & R. D. Roberts (Eds.), *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment* (pp. 53–70). Oxford: University Press.

Teige-Mocigemba, S., Penzl, B., Becker, M., Henn, L. & Klauer, K. C. (2016). Controlling the „uncontrollable“: Faking effects on the affect misattribution procedure. *Cognition and Emotion*, 30 (8), 1470–1484.

Tett, R. P., Freund, K. A., Christiansen, N. D., Fox, K. E. & Coaster, J. (2012). Faking on self-report emotional intelligence and personality tests: Effects of faking opportunity, cognitive ability, and job type. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 52 (2), 195–201.

Tett, R. P. & Simonet, D. V. (2011). Faking in personality assessment: A „multisaturation“ perspective on faking as performance. *Human Performance*, 24 (4), 302–321.

Viswesvaran, C. & Ones, D. S. (1999). Meta-analyses of fakability estimates: Implications for personality measurement. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 59 (2), 197–210.

Vries, R. E. de, Zettler, I., & Hilbig, B. E. (2014). Rethinking trait conceptions of social desirability scales: impression management as an expression of honesty-humility. *Assessment*, 21 (3), 286–299.

Weiss, B. & Feldmann, R. S. (2006). Looking good and lying to do it: Deception as an impression management strategy in job interviews. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 36 (4), 1070–1086.

Westhoff, K. (1993). Zur Übbarkeit konzentrierten Arbeitens. In K. J. Klauer (Hrsg.), *Kognitives Training* (S. 247–256). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Youngjohn, J. R., Lees-Haley, P. R., & Binder, L. M. (1999). Comment: Warning malingerers produces more sophisticated malingering. *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 14 (6), 511–515.

Yoxall, J., Bahr, M. & O'Neill, T. (2017). Faking bad in workers compensation psychological assessments: Elevation rates of negative distortion scales on the personality assessment inventory in an Australian sample. *Psychiatry, Psychology and Law*, 24 (5), 682–693.

Ziegler, M., MacCann, C. & Roberts, R. D. (2012). Faking: Knowns, unknowns, and points of contention. In M. Ziegler, C. MacCann & R. D. Roberts (Eds.), *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment* (pp. 3–16). Oxford: University Press.

Ziegler, M., Schmidt-Atzert, L., Bühner, M., & Krumm, S. (2007). Fakability of different measurement methods for achievement motivation: Questionnaire, semi-projective, and objective. *Psychology Science*, 49 (4), 291–307.